

Teachers' Metaphors Regarding Artificial Intelligence

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to explore teachers' metaphors regarding artificial intelligence. Today, artificial intelligence technologies are becoming increasingly prevalent in educational settings, significantly altering teaching practices, teachers' roles and the structure of learning environments. In this process of change, how teachers position artificial intelligence directly influences how this technology is used in education. Therefore, it is important to investigate what teachers liken artificial intelligence to and the underlying thoughts behind these analogies. As metaphors reveal how individuals make sense of complex and abstract concepts, they have been used as the primary data source in this study. A review of the literature reveals that artificial intelligence makes significant contributions to education, such as personalising learning, reducing teachers' workload, and supporting decision-making processes. Conversely, significant concerns such as ethical issues, the risk of dependency, the weakening of students' thinking and creative skills, and inequality of opportunity also attract attention.

The research was conducted using the phenomenology design, one of the qualitative research methods; data obtained from 12 teachers with different subject specialisms and levels of experience were analysed using content analysis. The findings reveal that teachers' views revolve around the themes of "access to information", "supporting learning", "the limited nature of interaction", "encouraging complacency" and "controlled use". The research found that teachers view artificial intelligence as a tool that provides rapid access to information, facilitates learning and supports the teaching process. However, participants stated that artificial intelligence has limitations when it comes to conveying emotions, taking individual differences into account and establishing value-based communication. Furthermore, views emerged suggesting that artificial intelligence could steer students towards ready-made information and potentially weaken critical thinking and creative processes. Nevertheless, teachers emphasised that, when used consciously and for pedagogical purposes, artificial intelligence could make significant contributions to the educational process. In this context, the research revealed that teachers perceive artificial intelligence as a multi-dimensional structure that encompasses both opportunities and risks. Consequently, it was concluded that pedagogical guidance, ethical awareness and conscious usage processes are crucial for the effective use of artificial intelligence in education.

KEYWORDS: Artificial intelligence, Metaphor, Teacher, Access to information

Cite the Article: ERDEM, A.R., GIDER, V. (2026). *Teachers' Metaphors Regarding Artificial Intelligence*. *Contemporary Research Analysis Journal*, 3(6), 458 – 465. <https://doi.org/10.55677/CRAJ/08-2026-Vol03I06>

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Publication Date: June 05, 2026

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, rapid developments in artificial intelligence technologies have led to significant changes in education systems, beginning to transform teaching processes, the structure of education and the understanding of learning. Artificial intelligence is paving the way for a new approach to education by making learning processes more flexible and adaptable to the individual, particularly through big data analysis, learning analytics and intelligent teaching systems (Ahmad et al., 2021; Chassignol et al., 2018). Whilst this transformation contributes to making learning more effective and efficient, it also brings with it a process that necessitates a rethinking of education systems. The impact of artificial intelligence in education is not limited to learning processes; it is also leading to significant changes in the roles and responsibilities of teachers. AI-supported systems reduce teachers' workload by providing support in areas such as assessment, content creation and student monitoring, thereby enabling teachers to focus more on the quality of the teaching process (Baker, 2019; Bryant et al., 2020). However, the role of teachers is not disappearing; rather, it is evolving into a position that guides, directs and gives meaning to the learning process (Felix, 2020; Zhao and Liu, 2018). This situation demonstrates that how teachers perceive and position artificial intelligence has become even more important.

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On the other hand, whilst artificial intelligence technologies offer significant opportunities in education, they also bring with them various risks. Whilst positive aspects such as the personalisation of learning, the enhancement of student achievement and the enrichment of teaching processes are highlighted, significant issues such as data security, ethical concerns, digital inequality and a tendency towards superficial learning among students also attract attention (Akyel and Tur, 2024; Altun, 2024; Boztepe, 2025). Furthermore, over-reliance on artificial intelligence carries the risk of undermining students' critical thinking and creative skills, whilst also highlighting the necessity of a balanced approach in education (Gül, 2024; Cooper, 2023). In this context, the effective and healthy use of artificial intelligence in education depends largely on how educational stakeholders interpret this technology. The literature indicates that teachers' and students' views on artificial intelligence are generally multifaceted. Research indicates that individuals predominantly describe artificial intelligence using metaphors such as 'brain, human, universe, teacher', and that this perspective is largely grounded in a technological framework (Erdoğan and Bozkurt, 2023; Gölbaşı and Okul, 2024). However, some studies reveal that these views have become more complex over time and that artificial intelligence is perceived as both an opportunity and a risk (Seyrek et al., 2024). This indicates that views on artificial intelligence are based not only on knowledge but also on experiences, value judgements and emotional assessments. At this point, metaphors emerge as a key tool for revealing how teachers interpret artificial intelligence. Metaphors enable individuals to express their mental world, experiences and perspectives in a clearer and more concrete manner. In particular, metaphors provide a powerful source of data for understanding how teachers perceive artificial intelligence, a complex and abstract concept. In this context, what teachers liken artificial intelligence to and the reasons they give for these comparisons provide important insights into the nature of artificial intelligence's use in education. In this regard, investigating teachers' metaphors regarding artificial intelligence will contribute to the development of more conscious, balanced and pedagogically grounded approaches to the use of artificial intelligence in education.

METHOD

This study was designed as a qualitative research project aiming to elicit teachers' views on artificial intelligence through metaphors. The qualitative approach offers a robust framework for revealing how individuals interpret a phenomenon, the experiences on which their interpretations are based, and how they express these meanings (Creswell, 2014). In this regard, the study aims to reveal not only the ways in which teachers define artificial intelligence but also the meanings they ascribe to this concept.

RESEARCH DESIGN

A phenomenological research design was adopted for this study. Phenomenology focuses on an in-depth examination of individuals' experiences of a particular phenomenon and the meanings they ascribe to these experiences (Merriam, 2013). In this study, artificial intelligence was treated as a phenomenon that teachers encounter directly but interpret in different ways. Consequently, what teachers liken artificial intelligence to and the reasons they give for these analogies have been assessed as an important source of data for understanding their mental and professional positioning.

STUDY GROUP

The study group consists of a total of 12 secondary school teachers working at different levels. When selecting participants, the maximum diversity sampling method was used to reflect different experiences and perspectives. Maximum diversity sampling aims to bring together individuals with different characteristics related to the research topic in order to examine the subject from a broad perspective. The key aspect of this approach is to identify whether there are commonalities across different situations and to highlight the various dimensions of the problem through this diversity (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2000). Accordingly, purposive sampling was employed in the study; 12 secondary school teachers working in four different primary schools were included in the study group. Variables such as gender, subject specialism, age and professional experience were taken into account when selecting participants. This approach prevented the data from reflecting a single perspective, thereby ensuring that views on artificial intelligence were presented in a more comprehensive manner. A table detailing the participants' demographic characteristics is provided below.

Table 1. Demographic variables of the participants

Participant	Gender	Subject	Age	Years of Service
K1	Female	Turkish	29	3
K2	Male	Mathematics	34	7
K3	Male	Science	40	14
K4	Male	Social Studies	38	15
K5	Female	English	30	5
K6	Male	Religious Culture and Ethics	41	18
K7	Female	Mathematics	33	6

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K8	Male	Turkish	44	21
K9	Female	Science	37	11
K10	Male	Social Studies	31	8
K11	Female	English	43	16
K12	Male	Religious Culture and Ethics	46	23

An examination of Table 1 reveals that the teachers participating in the study exhibited a balanced distribution in terms of gender; however, it is evident that the views of participants selected from different subject areas regarding artificial intelligence may vary depending on the characteristics of their teaching fields and their experience. When the variables of professional seniority and age are considered together, the inclusion of teachers at different career stages contributes to the findings reflecting a diversity of experience; it also reveals that teachers' interpretations of artificial intelligence may change alongside their professional experience. The fact that all participants work at secondary school level clarifies the context of the research and allows the findings to be evaluated within the framework of a specific educational level.

Data Collection and Analysis

In the research, an open-ended questionnaire—developed by the researchers and reviewed in terms of scope and wording in line with the views of subject matter experts—was used as the data collection tool. The open-ended statement included in the form was created with the contribution of two subject matter experts; based on feedback obtained during the pilot application process, points that did not sufficiently serve the purpose were revised, and the final version of the form was established. During the data collection process, a single guiding statement was used to enable participants to express their views on artificial intelligence in depth. In this context, participants were asked to complete the sentence “Artificial intelligence is like ... because ...” based on their own experiences and thoughts. Within this framework, metaphors are regarded as powerful tools that reflect how individuals perceive a phenomenon, the experiences on which their understanding is based, and how they situate it within their mental world (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). Furthermore, this approach enabled participants to articulate, in their own words, the concepts through which they understood artificial intelligence and the reasons underpinning these analogies, thereby facilitating the evaluation of an abstract concept within a more concrete and comprehensible framework. Meanwhile, the data obtained were analysed using content analysis. During the analysis process, the metaphors created by the teachers were first examined carefully, and the meaning expressed by each metaphor was identified. Subsequently, metaphors carrying similar meanings were grouped together under specific categories, and higher-level themes were developed based on these categories. In this process, alongside the metaphors, the reasons participants gave for these analogies were also taken into account and incorporated into the interpretation. The aim of the analysis was to go beyond the surface-level analogies and reveal, in greater depth, the underlying thought processes, experiences and assessments that underpin the teachers' views on artificial intelligence.

Validity and Reliability

In order to enhance the reliability of the findings obtained in the study, the analysis process was conducted in a careful and systematic manner. In this context, the data were reviewed repeatedly, and care was taken to ensure consistency throughout the coding and interpretation process. Furthermore, to prevent the researchers' interpretations from remaining subjective, the findings were supported by direct quotations from the participants' own statements. This approach strengthens the study's credibility by clarifying the relationship between the data source and the interpretations made. Such practices, aimed at ensuring validity and reliability in qualitative research, align with the fundamental methodological principles that contribute to the study producing reliable and meaningful results (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

FINDINGS

As a result of the analysis process, it was determined that participants' views on artificial intelligence, in line with their perspectives, fell under the themes of access to information, support for learning, limitations of the interaction dimension, tendency towards convenience, and controlled use. These themes and their associated codes are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Themes, sub-themes and codes based on participants' views

Themes	Sub-themes	Codes	Participants
Access to Information	Providing quick and extensive information	Librarian, Calculator	K1, K2
	Providing quick and extensive information	Compass, Magnifying Glass	K4, K9
Supporting Learning	Facilitating learning	Teaching Assistant, Guide	K2, K10
	Generating original ideas	Author, Designer	K8, K12
	Shortening the learning steps	Summariser	K3, K4
Limited Interaction	Inability to convey emotion and meaning	Superficial narrator, Emotionless System	K1, K12

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	Inability to tailor to the individual	Top-down narrator	K2, K7, K11
	Inability to establish value-based communication	Non-exemplary system	K6, K10
Encouraging complacency	Reaching conclusions without effort	Provider of ready-made answers	K8, K9
	Process Guidance	Guiding System	K1, K4
Controlled Use	Two-way influence	Double-edged sword	K4, K12
	Outcome dependent on use	Directable Tool	K6, K7, K10

Theme of access to information

When examining the metaphors teachers used in relation to artificial intelligence in the study, the theme of 'Access to Information' emerged as the most prominent. Under this theme, teachers viewed artificial intelligence as a tool that enables rapid access to information, can provide versatile content, and makes information visible. In the participants' statements, particular emphasis was placed on AI's ability to "provide fast and extensive information", access a large amount of information in a short time, present different examples, and generate content that supports the learning process. However, some teachers also noted that, whilst AI facilitates access to information, it cannot fully reflect the emotional and meaningful dimensions rooted in human experience. In this context, some of the participants' views are as follows.

"I liken artificial intelligence to a librarian who works very quickly but cannot always think deeply. This is because it can access a great deal of information in a very short time, generate text, produce summaries and present different examples to students. However, it cannot always fully grasp the emotion, context or subtleties derived from human experience within a text. In a Turkish lesson, it can explain a poem, but it certainly cannot interpret the loneliness, joy or hurt the student feels in that poem as deeply as the connection the teacher establishes." (K1)

"I liken artificial intelligence to a well-programmed, advanced calculator. Because it doesn't just give the result; sometimes it can also explain the steps of the solution. It can help students spot their own mistakes, as well as demonstrate different ways of solving problems." (K2).

Under the second code for this theme, "Making Knowledge Visible", participants emphasised that artificial intelligence supports the learning process by making complex information more understandable, organised and concrete, and that it is a tool that facilitates learning and supports the teaching process, as follows:

"I liken artificial intelligence to a versatile but directional compass. Because it makes it easier to access a wealth of information on history, geography, citizenship and current affairs. Students can quickly acquire information about different countries, events and cultures." (K4)

"I liken artificial intelligence to a powerful magnifying glass. Because when used correctly, it makes details visible that the student cannot see. In science lessons, students may sometimes fail to recognise the system behind natural phenomena. Artificial intelligence can explain the cause, effect and mechanism of an event in a more understandable way, using clear examples—just as a magnifying glass reveals every detail—thereby increasing the student's interest in the subject." (K9).

The theme of supporting learning

The other theme was identified by participants as "Supporting Learning". This theme comprises the sub-themes of "facilitating learning", "generating original ideas" and "shortening the learning process". Under the first sub-theme, "Facilitating Learning", participants stated that artificial intelligence helps students understand topics more easily and supports the teaching process. Some of the participants' comments on this are as follows.

"It doesn't just provide the answer; sometimes it can also explain the steps of the solution. It can help the student spot their mistakes and show different ways to solve the problem." (K2)

"I see artificial intelligence as a supporting teacher. It provides support, particularly in large classes where we cannot attend to every student." (K10).

Under the sub-theme "Generating Original Ideas", participants noted that artificial intelligence can contribute to students developing creative ideas by presenting different ways of thinking, as follows:

"I sometimes think of artificial intelligence as a writer; because it can produce different and eye-catching ideas in a short time. It's particularly wonderful that it offers alternatives I wouldn't have thought of when writing text or preparing activities" (K8).

"In my view, artificial intelligence is like a designer; because when producing visual content, it can come up with ideas that go beyond the conventional. This can also be used to develop students' imagination." (K14).

Under the other sub-theme, 'Shortening the Learning Steps', participants expressed that artificial intelligence can make the learning process shorter and more practical by providing rapid access to information, as follows:

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"In my view, artificial intelligence acts as a catalyst; because it can present complex processes in a concise and understandable way during experiments or subject explanations. This enables students to reach the conclusion more quickly." (K3)

"In my view, artificial intelligence acts as a summariser; because it can present lengthy topics in a short time, highlighting the key points. This streamlines the learning process and enables students to access information quickly." (K4)

The theme of limited interaction

Under the theme of *"Limitations of the Interaction Dimension"*, participants stated that artificial intelligence makes significant contributions in terms of providing information and supporting learning; however, it has certain limitations when it comes to conveying emotions, taking individual differences into account, and establishing value-based communication. This theme comprises the sub-themes of *"inability to convey emotion and meaning"*, *"inability to tailor to the individual"*, and *"inability to establish value-based communication"*. Under the first sub-theme, *"Inability to Convey Emotion and Meaning"*, participants emphasised that whilst artificial intelligence can generate accurate information and content, it fails to adequately reflect the emotional dimension of the learning process. Participants also stated that artificial intelligence is not as effective as human interaction in fostering feelings, empathy and values in students, as follows:

"Artificial intelligence generates text and can construct correct sentences, but it cannot fully reflect the emotion behind the text. It often leaves the point the student needs to feel at a superficial level." (K1)

"There are certain values we wish to instil in students, and these are learned not just by being told, but by being felt. I believe artificial intelligence falls short in creating this sense of feeling." (K12)

Under the second sub-theme, *"Inability to Provide Individualised Guidance"*, participants emphasised that artificial intelligence fails to take sufficient account of students' individual differences, levels of readiness and emotional needs; they noted that AI often falls short in developing guidance tailored to students' interests, curiosity and learning pace by presenting standardised content. Their comments on this matter are as follows:

"Not every student learns at the same pace, but artificial intelligence often presents a one-size-fits-all narrative. This disregards individual differences." (K11)

"Presenting the same content without taking into account the student's interest, curiosity or readiness is a significant shortcoming." (K2)

"Artificial intelligence is merely a system that provides information; however, it cannot develop a narrative that takes into account the student's curiosity, excitement or anxiety, treating everyone the same. Consequently, it falls short in terms of establishing an emotional connection during the learning process." (K7)

Under the third sub-theme, *"Failure to Establish Value-Based Communication"*, participants noted that whilst artificial intelligence can facilitate the transfer of information, it remains limited in terms of imparting values, serving as a role model, and fostering human relationships, as follows:

"Students learn by observing behaviour. As artificial intelligence cannot serve as a role model, it falls short in the process of instilling values." (K10)

"Concepts such as respect and empathy can only develop through relationships with humans, and artificial intelligence cannot provide this." (K6)

The theme of encouraging complacency

Another theme highlighted by the participants was *"Encouraging Complacency"*. Within this theme, which comprises the sub-themes of *"reaching conclusions without producing work"* and *"manipulating the process"*, participants noted that although artificial intelligence accelerates the learning process, it may have certain negative effects on students' abilities to think, produce work and manage the process. Under the first sub-theme, *"Reaching the Outcome Without Production"*, participants noted that artificial intelligence can sometimes divert students away from the process of research, thinking and production, directing them straight to the outcome. Participants particularly emphasised that rapid access to ready-made information can weaken students' active participation in the learning process and hinder lasting learning. Their assessments on this matter are as follows:

"Thanks to artificial intelligence, students reach the result very quickly; however, as they do not generate the solution themselves during this process, long-term learning is weakened." (K9)

"Instead of constructing sentences, students receive direct translations. This reduces active participation in the language learning process." (K8)

Under the second sub-theme, *"Guiding the Process"*, participants noted that artificial intelligence does not merely provide information but can also guide students' thinking patterns and the learning process, and that it can sometimes limit students' independent thinking skills, as follows:

"When writing, students stick to the framework provided by artificial intelligence rather than forming their own ideas. Furthermore, as artificial intelligence determines which information is important in subject learning, students are unable to manage the process themselves." (K1)

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"Artificial intelligence can also guide how we interpret information. This situation can limit the student's ability to think independently." (K4)

The theme of controlled use

The final theme identified by the participants was *"Controlled Use"*. Within this theme, participants emphasised that, whilst artificial intelligence presents significant opportunities in the educational process, it also entails various risks; consequently, the manner in which it is used is crucial. This theme comprises the sub-themes *"two-way impact"* and *"outcomes dependent on usage"*. Under the first sub-theme, *"Two-way Impact"*, participants noted that whilst artificial intelligence has positive aspects such as facilitating learning and accelerating access to information, it also carries the risk of weakening students' critical thinking, research and reasoning skills. The relevant assessments are set out below.

"It provides quick access to information but also carries the risk of weakening the student's ability to question. Benefit and risk go hand in hand." (K12)

"On the one hand, it makes complex topics easier to understand; on the other, it can reduce the student's need to conduct research. If it focuses solely on the outcome, learning does not take place. That is why it has a two-way effect." (K4)

Under the second sub-theme, *"Outcome Dependent on Use"*, participants noted that the impact of artificial intelligence is largely dependent on its intended purpose and user awareness. Participants emphasised that, with proper guidance, artificial intelligence can become a powerful tool supporting the teaching process; however, when used unconsciously, it can lead to superficial learning, as follows.

"I see it as a double-edged sword. It is beneficial if used correctly, but harmful if used incorrectly. In particular, the aspect of generating ready-made homework weakens the student." (K6)

"It is effective when used for language practice; however, when used as a ready-made translation tool, its contribution to learning diminishes." (K7)

"The benefit derived from artificial intelligence depends on user awareness. If properly guided, it is a powerful support; otherwise, it becomes a superficial tool." (K10)

According to the research findings, teachers view artificial intelligence as an important tool that facilitates access to information, supports learning and accelerates the teaching process. Participants highlighted artificial intelligence's ability to provide rapid access to information, offer alternative solutions, make complex content more comprehensible and support the teaching process. However, teachers' views indicate that artificial intelligence is assessed not merely as a technical tool, but as a multi-dimensional structure with effects on learning, thinking and human relationships. In particular, statements regarding facilitating learning, generating original ideas and supporting the teaching process reveal that artificial intelligence is positioned as an auxiliary learning support within educational settings. Participants emphasised that artificial intelligence cannot fully replace human interaction in terms of conveying emotions, developing empathy, taking individual differences into account, and establishing value-based communication. Furthermore, risks such as students relying on ready-made information, reaching conclusions without engaging in the process of creation, and a decline in independent thinking skills were highlighted. This suggests that teachers view artificial intelligence not as an entirely positive or negative entity, but rather as a dual-purpose tool that can present both benefits and risks depending on how it is used. Consequently, the findings indicate that pedagogical guidance, ethical awareness, student-centred guidance and informed usage processes are crucial for the effective use of artificial intelligence in education.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

When the research findings are evaluated, it is evident that teachers view artificial intelligence as a multifaceted tool that provides rapid access to information and offers significant opportunities within the educational process, yet one that requires careful management. Participants highlighted AI's ability to provide rapid access to information, make complex content more understandable, offer alternative solutions, and support the teaching process. This finding aligns with research in the literature regarding the potential of artificial intelligence to personalise learning, support teaching processes, and enhance learning efficiency (Ahmad et al., 2021; Chassignol et al., 2018). Teachers' descriptions of artificial intelligence using metaphors such as "librarian", "teaching assistant", "compass" and "guide" reveal that this technology is positioned as a supportive tool that facilitates access to information and supports learning within the teaching process. Views suggesting that artificial intelligence can provide support to teachers, particularly in situations where individual support is limited in large classes, indicate that teachers do not perceive artificial intelligence as a complete threat, but rather as a supportive element in the teaching process. This finding is consistent with research suggesting that the role of the teacher has not disappeared; rather, it has evolved into a structure that guides, directs and gives meaning to the learning process (Felix, 2020; Zhao and Liu, 2018).

Another notable finding in the research is that teachers do not view artificial intelligence merely as a technical tool, but also question its effects on learning, thinking and human relationships. Participants particularly emphasised that artificial intelligence remains limited in terms of conveying emotions, developing empathy, taking individual differences into account and establishing value-based communication. The fact that teachers used metaphors such as 'emotionless system', 'superficial narrator' and 'system that cannot serve as a role model' demonstrates that education is not viewed as merely the transfer of information; it

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also encompasses dimensions of emotion, values and human interaction. This indicates that teachers perceive artificial intelligence as a structure with certain pedagogical limitations. In particular, the view that human interaction is indispensable in areas such as values education, empathy, serving as a role model, and understanding the student's emotional needs is coming to the fore. Indeed, studies on artificial intelligence in education also emphasise that whilst technology can provide cognitive support, it cannot fully replace human interaction in emotional, social and ethical dimensions (Cooper, 2023; Gül, 2024).

On the other hand, the findings also indicate that teachers harbour significant concerns regarding artificial intelligence. Participants highlighted risks such as students relying on ready-made information, moving away from research and critical thinking processes, showing a tendency to reach conclusions without engaging in the creative process, and a decline in their ability to think independently. The metaphors of the "ready-answer provider" and the "guiding system" highlight teachers' concerns that, whilst artificial intelligence may facilitate the learning process, it could simultaneously render students passive. This finding aligns with research indicating that the unconscious use of artificial intelligence may lead to superficial learning and a decline in students' higher-order thinking skills (Altun, 2024; Boztepe, 2025). In particular, teachers' emphasis on students focusing on the direct outcome rather than the process highlights the importance of pedagogical guidance in the use of artificial intelligence in education. Although artificial intelligence is a powerful tool that supports learning, when used without the teacher's guidance, it can distance the student from the processes of thinking, questioning and creating.

Another key finding of the research is that teachers do not view artificial intelligence as an entirely positive or entirely negative entity. Participants stated that the impact of artificial intelligence depends largely on the manner of its use, user awareness, and the guidance provided during the teaching process. The metaphors of the 'double-edged sword' and the 'steerable tool' demonstrate that artificial intelligence is viewed as a construct that presents both opportunities and risks simultaneously. This indicates that teachers do not adopt an approach of outright resistance to technology; on the contrary, they embrace a controlled, informed and pedagogically grounded approach to its use. Teachers' views indicate that for artificial intelligence to be used effectively in education, not only technical competence but also ethical awareness, critical thinking, digital literacy and pedagogical guidance are required. Consequently, it is understood that the use of artificial intelligence in educational settings must be approached not merely as a technological transformation, but as a holistic process of change encompassing pedagogical, ethical and human dimensions. Overall, the research reveals that teachers view artificial intelligence as a powerful tool to support educational processes; however, it also highlights that this technology has aspects that require careful management in terms of human interaction, the transmission of values, independent thinking and conscious use. The views expressed by teachers through metaphors indicate that the role of artificial intelligence in education should not be framed solely in terms of technical benefits, but must also be considered within the context of pedagogical, ethical and human dimensions. In this regard, it is important to support teachers' digital and pedagogical competencies, equip students with the skills to use AI critically and responsibly, strengthen ethical awareness, and position AI as a tool that supports the teaching process.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmad, S. F., Rahmat, M. K., Mubarik, M. S., Alam, M. M., & Hyder, S. I. (2021). Artificial intelligence and its role in education. *Sustainability*, 13(22), 2-11.
2. Akyel, Y., ve Tur, E. (2024). Eğitim bilimlerinde yapay zekânın potansiyeli ve beklentiler, zorluklar ve gelecek yönelimleri. *Ahi Evran Üniversitesi Kırşehir Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 25(1), 645-711. <https://doi.org/10.29299/kefad.1322341>
3. Altun, E. (2024). Yapay zekâ ve pedagoji: Eğitimde fırsatlar ve zorluklar. *Dijital Teknolojiler ve Eğitim Dergisi*, 3(1), 80-95.
4. Arslan, K. (2020). Eğitimde yapay zeka ve uygulamaları. *Batı Anadolu Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 11(1), 71-88.
5. Baker, R. S., & Inventado, P. S. (2014). Educational data mining and learning analytics. In J. A. Larusson & B. White (Eds.), *Learning analytics: From research to practice* (pp. 61-75). Springer.
6. Boztepe, C. (2025). Eğitimde yapay zekâ uygulamaları: Fırsatlar, sınırlılıklar ve etik tartışmalar. *Dumlupınar Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 9(1), 98-121. <https://doi.org/10.71272/debder.1706141>
7. Chassignol, M., Khoroshavin, A., Klimova, A., & Bilyatdinova, A. (2018). Artificial intelligence trends in education: A narrative overview. *Procedia Computer Science*, 136, 16-24.
8. Cooper, G. (2023). Examining science education in ChatGPT: An exploratory study of generative artificial intelligence. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 32, 444-452.
9. Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE.
10. Çam, M. B., Çelik, N. C., Turan-Güntepe, E., & Durukan, Ü. G. (2021). Öğretmen adaylarının yapay zekâ teknolojileri ile ilgili farkındalıklarının belirlenmesi. *Hatay Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 18(48), 263-285.
11. Felix, C. V. (2020). The role of the teacher and AI in education. In *International perspectives on the role of technology in humanizing higher education*. Emerald Publishing.

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12. Gölbaşı, B., & Okul, Ö. (2024). Öğretmen adaylarının “yapay zekâ” kavramına ilişkin metaforik alguları. In *XI. International Eurasian Educational Research Congress* (pp. 49–58). Eurasian Educational Research Association.
13. Gül, F. Ö. (2024). Eğitimde yapay zekâ: eğitim fakültesi akademisyenleri için fırsatlar ve riskler. *Medeniyet Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 8(2), 71-97.
14. Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial intelligence in education: Promises and implications for teaching and learning*. Center for Curriculum Redesign.
15. Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. University of Chicago Press.
16. Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. SAGE.
17. Luckin, R. (2018). *Machine learning and human intelligence: The future of education for the 21st century*. UCL IOE Press.
18. Merriam, S. B. (2013). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation* (3rd ed.). Jossey-Bass.
19. Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook* (2nd ed.). SAGE.
20. Nguyen, A., Ngo, H. N., Hong, Y., Dang, B., & Nguyen, B. P. T. (2023). Ethical principles for artificial intelligence in education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28, 4221–4241.
21. Patton, M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods* (3rd ed.). SAGE.
22. Porayska-Pomsta, K., Holmes, W., & Nemorin, S. (2023/2024). *The Ethics of Artificial Intelligence in Education*. Routledge.
23. Selwyn, N. (2019). *Should robots replace teachers? AI and the future of education*. Polity Press.
24. Seyrek, M. (2024). Öğretmenlerin eğitimde yapay zekâ kullanımına yönelik görüşleri. *Journal of Social, Humanities and Administrative Sciences Studies*, 10(2), 215–228.
25. Tack, A., & Piech, C. (2022). *The AI teacher test: Measuring the pedagogical ability of Blender and GPT-3 in educational dialogues* (pp. 1–16). arXiv.
26. UNESCO. (2021). *AI and education: Guidance for policy-makers*. UNESCO.